

Screen Time: Risks Awareness and Perception of Undergraduates in Northeast Universities, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines undergraduates' awareness and perception of risks associated with the use of screen-based devices like smartphones, laptops and desktop computers. A total of 437 students from Modibbo Adama University of Technology, Yola and Taraba State University Jalingo have been surveyed. Data collected through questionnaire have been analyzed using descriptive statistical tools (frequency and simple percentages). Findings show that students within the surveyed universities are frequently exposed to screen devices and that they are aware that excessive use of screen devices could be risky to their health, social and physical life. However, most of the students do not take proactive measures to mitigate these risks. Therefore, the study calls on university authorities and the mass media to lead a campaign toward enlightening the students on the need to take precautionary measures while using screen-based devices. It also recommends that government agencies and groups like Consumer Protection Council of Nigeria and Standard Organization of Nigeria should compel producers of mobile screen-devices to improve safety measures in their products.

Keywords: Screen Time, Risks, Awareness, Perception, Undergraduates

Introduction

Information and communication technologies (ICT) devices such as desktop computers, smart-phones, tablets, laptops, video games, e-books, televisions, internet among others are the fastest growing technologies not just in developed nations but in developing nations. These screen-based technologies are becoming more and more popular and affecting people's daily life. Devices like mobile phones and iPhones have become much more than a device for calls and text messaging but cultural artifacts that are associated with individuals social, professional and academic life. Mobile devices like Smart-phones are noticeable in public; people are often glued to these devices everywhere from buses, planes, bars, shops and high streets. A survey by Ruder Finn, one of the world's largest, independent public relations agencies says people in the U.S.A are spending an average of 2.7 hours on the mobile screen devices and internet –connecting socially, managing their personal finances, and even as a means for advocacy (Caplan, 2010). This situation is not just in the United States but applicable to almost all nations of the world especially among college or university students.

Today, screen devices like smartphone and laptop have become integral to the daily life of students. Students are closer to screen-based devices like never before. Sigma (2012) asserts that from the

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moment students get up from bed until the time they go to bed again including when they are eating, exercising and reading, students are using their smart-phones, tablets, computers, laptops and other electronic devices. Electronic screen activities such as surfing the internet, chatting, and watching movies on laptop, video games are common activities of undergraduates. Several studies globally (Omotayo, 2006, Leung 2015) revealed that young undergraduates spend up to 11 hours per day using screen-based technologies such as smart-phones, tablets, computers and television.

In Nigeria particularly, many studies (Ani 2010, Omotayo 2006, Awoleye, Siyanbola and Oladipo 2008 among others) have confirmed that internet use is common among undergraduates in Nigeria. These studies have focused on the various purposes students in Nigeria used internet and the time they spent on it. Awoleye, Siyanbola and Oladapo (2008) discovered that internet is use among students in Nigeria for information development, easy communication, improved academic performance, as a research tool, provides solution to assignments, and gives information on entertainment and a source of scholarship. Ani (2010) and Adum, Ekwugha, Ojiakor and Ebeze (2016) opine that College students are attracted to mobile screen-based devices for a variety of reasons, including their ability to easily access the web and or popular social networking sites. They explain further that college students are always on screen to keep up with what their friends are doing as well as exchange messages and find out the latest trends among their age group.

Nevertheless, prolonged screen time for any reason can result to harmful effects on one's physical, social and health life. Martin (2011) adds that spending hours on screen-based devices can affect the users' vision or sight both immediately and over a lifetime. The New Zealand Ministry of Health (NZMOH, 2013) cited in MacMullin, Jonathan and Weiss (2015) warns that prolonged use of electronic screen products will lead to eye and visual symptoms like ocular discomfort, eyestrain, dry eye, headache, blurred vision and even double vision. It further stresses that screen time leads to poor sleep habits and patterns.

In view of the rapid use of screen devices such as computers, video games, e-books, televisions, smart-phones and the likely risks on the users' health, developed nations like Australia, have set guidelines to regulate children and young people use of screen-based devices (America Academy of Pediatrics, 2001). The America Academy of Pediatrics (AAP) in her guidelines and campaigns concerning screen time, advised that youth need not to have access to the internet or TV in their bedrooms and that parents need to monitor media use of their children (AAP, 2013). This kind of proactive step appears to be missing in developing nations like Nigeria even with record of rapid internet and screen device exposure. This necessitates individual precautions against the implication of excessive screen time. However, individuals can only take precautionary measures if they are aware and have positive views regarding the risks associated with the use of screen based devices.

It is against this backdrop that this study examines the awareness and perception of undergraduates in Northeast Universities of Nigeria toward risks associated with screen time. This becomes expedient considering the increasing availability and affordability of wireless screen devices and affordable data plans by telecommunication companies which are playing a major role in the growing use of screen-based technologies among the students.

Research Questions

The following questions were formulated to guide the study achieve its objectives:

- i. To what extent are undergraduates in Northeast Universities of Nigeria exposed to screen-based electronic devices?
- ii. What is the awareness of risks associated with screen time among undergraduates in Northeast Universities of Nigeria?
- iii. What is the perception of undergraduates in Northeast Universities of Nigeria toward risks associated with screen time?

Conceptual/Literature Review

The Concept of Screen Time

Screen time is the viewing or use of anything with a screen, most especially Smartphone, TV, video games, laptops and desktop computers. Screen time activities include watching television, playing video games and going online or surfing of the internet (Busch, Manders, and Leeuw, 2013). For almost a decade now, there has been a tremendous rise in screen time activities among children and youth across the globe. For example, in Britain, children by the age of 10 years have regular access to an average of five different screens at home (U.K Health and Safety Executive, 2016). In addition to the main family television, many young people have their own bedroom TV along with portable handheld computer game consoles (e.g., Nintendo, Play-station, Xbox), smart-phone with games, internet and video, a family computer and a laptop and/or a tablet computer. Several studies have identified reasons young people especially students spend time on screen devices. Studies (Gagnon and Krovi, 2000; Jagboro, 2003; Kaur, 2005) report that undergraduates engaged in screen time especially via internet to search for information and or articles for their assignments, connect with friends on social media among others. However, excessive screen time for any purpose is not without some implications on the user.

Risks of Excessive Screen Time

The expanding screen-use culture of the youth is a source of concern, as research indicates that excessive screen time is associated with health and wellbeing adversity for young people. One study

of Scottish youth further found that total screen time predicted psychological distress independent of physical activity levels (Hamer, Stamatakis, and Mishra, 2009) while another study of Australian adolescents found that excessive screen time predicted increased loneliness, depression, anxiety, attention problems, and aggression (Martin, 2011). Messias, Castro, Saini, Usman and Peebles (2011) found that excessive amounts of screen time, particularly internet activity and video gaming predicted more sadness, suicidal ideation and suicide planning among American teens. In addition, a study of Norwegian teens demonstrated that a combination of more television, video and computer use lead to more back pain and headaches (Torsheim, Eriksson, Schnohr, Hansen, Bjarnason and Vålímáa, 2010).

In another development, prolonged use of computer and related screen devices is found to be associated with Computer Vision Syndrome (CVS), a group of eye and vision-related problems that result from using computer for a prolonged period. According to Vision Watch (2014.), two broad categories of symptoms exist in CVS. The first group, terms external symptoms, include burning, irritation, ocular dryness and tearing, and is related to dry eye. The second group, terms internal symptoms, include eyestrain, headache, eye ache, blurred and double vision, and is generally caused by refractive, accommodative or vergence anomalies. The most common symptoms are dry eyes, headache, eyestrain, neck and shoulder pain as well as blurred vision. The level of discomfort increases with the amount of computer use and will decline after stopping computer work. Reviews in CVS show significant amount of computer users may experience CVS symptoms vision at either near or when looking into the distance after prolonged computer use (Eldeeb and Gopal, 2014).

The National Institutes of Health–American Association of Retired Persons Diet and Health Study (1995 and 1996) cohort has given important insights into the link between screen time and cancer. It consisted of a prospective cohort study of 488,720 men and women aged 50 to 71 years at baseline from 1995 to 1996. It found out that high levels of screen time through Television, video watching and surfing of internet were associated with an increased risk of colon cancer for men and women and endometrial cancer in women. In addition, Mobile phones have been shown to be the likely cause of headache, extreme irritation, increased carelessness, forgetfulness, poorer reflexes and a clicking sound in the ears (Rai, Saroshe, Khatri, Sirohi and Dixit, 2016).

Furthermore, it is revealed that prolonged use of electronic screen products in a fixed posture could cause or exacerbate musculoskeletal symptoms. It is advisable to adopt ergonomic measures and regular breaks with relaxation exercise to avoid over stressing the muscles. In the same vein, studies have shown a directly proportional relationship between obesity and screen time (Shields, 2006; AAP, 2011; Harvard School of Public Health, 2014). Harvard School of Public Health says that children logging over two hours of screen time per day are twice likely to be overweight or obese than peers watching one hour or less per day. Children tend to crave and eat sugary or starchy food during the

day to provide energy to stay awake and they tend to eat snacks and or “junks” while sitting down to watch television, play computer games and engage in online chatting. Apart from obesity, nighttime screen time is associated with shortened sleep duration, poorer diet quality, and lower physical activity levels.

Despina, Byington and David (2009) establish that screen time activities like chatting and watching clips on Smart-phone while on highway are distractive and dangerous. Using data from the US Consumer Product Safety Commission on injuries in hospital emergency rooms from 2004 to 2010, they found that mobile phone related injuries among both pedestrians and drivers increased. Road Traffic Accident Statistics of Hong Kong (2013) concurs that there is an increasing alert of incidents of falling or straining in escalators in public areas such as train stations and malls due to the use of mobile electronic screen products in Hong Kong.

Extent of Screen Time among Students

There have been plethora of studies on the frequency or time people spend with screen-based devices. Larson (1996) opines that utilization of screen-based devices varies, among age brackets and occupations. According to him, younger generation have more time at their disposal than those in their 30s and 40s, who could not use much of the time for social activities online or on their devices. However, most studies on time spent with screen-device among students do not necessary focus on age variable. Bao (1998) surveyed internet use at Seton Hall University. The findings of the study showed that 40.2% of the respondents used the Web on a daily basis, 38.3% weekly, and 10.7% on a monthly basis. About 10% respondents said they seldom or never used the internet. He concluded that screen time among the students is high and has tendency to grow.

Davis, Smith, Rodrigue and Pulvers (1999) used a questionnaire to compare internet use at a small, private liberal arts university and a medium-size, public state university in Texas. They found that 91% of the students on both campuses accessed the internet for about 25 hours per week. Anderson (2001) studied 1,302 college students (649 men, 647 women) from seven colleges in the Northeastern U.S. and one in Ireland using a 69-question survey. The results indicated that on the average; students spent about 100 minutes per day on screen device. Browsing and gaming is the major activity of these students during screen time. Ozoemelem (2010) studied screen time via internet among undergraduates in Delta State University, Abraka, Nigeria, it was found that 63.33% of undergraduates at the University spent thirty minutes to one hour per day on digital device surfing the internet. Adekunmisi, Ajala and Iyoro (2013) in a survey of internet access and usage by undergraduates of Olabisi Onabanjo University, Nigeria found out that the respondents spent 1-2 hours daily on the internet. Sarwar and Soomro’s (2013) survey, indicates that 33% of mobile workers

admitted that they check their phones for mails or messages throughout the night. Nearly 50% of those surveyed said, they would not even think of going to bed without their Smartphone's tucked under their pillows (Yun, Kettinger and Lee, 2012 and Fischer and Smolnik, 2013). All studies above point to the fact that there is high exposure to screen based devices among students across the world and Nigeria in particular.

Awareness of the Risks Associated with Screen Time among Students

Adum, Ekwugha, Ojiakor and Ebeze (2016) studied students' awareness of the health implications associated with the use of screen devices in Southeast Nigeria. Findings generally indicate that university students in Southeast Nigeria have a high level of awareness of the possible health implications associated with the use of screen-based devices, as most of them claim to have experienced one form of health challenge or another in the course of using the devices. Leung and Lee (2015) studied the interrelationships among internet literacy, internet addiction symptoms, internet activities, and academic performance in Hong Kong. Results show most of the respondents are aware of some risk related to excessive time on screen devices but the benefit of screen devices make them addictive despite perceived risks.

MacMullin, Lunskey and Weiss (2015) further document patterns and impact of electronics use in individuals with autism spectrum disorder compared to typically developing peers. Participants included 172 parents of typically developing individuals and 139 parents of individuals with an autism spectrum disorder diagnosis, ranging in age from 6 to 21 years. Parents completed an online survey of demographics and the frequency, duration, and problematic patterns of electronics use in their youth and young adults. Parents reported that their children do not necessarily see any risk in computer or internet addiction. Best, Taylor, Manktelow and McQuilkin (2013) appraised the performance of eight databases to retrieve research pertaining to the influence of social networking sites on the mental health of young people. A total of 43 empirical studies on young people's use of social networking sites and the mental health implications were retrieved. It was revealed that there has not been sufficient knowledge or empirical literature on the implication of social network activities on the health of young people. By implication, large numbers of students are aware of the risk associated with screen time.

Perception of Students toward Risks Associated with Screen Time

Kumar, Chuan, Rajendaran (2011) studied perception of potential health hazards of using mobile phone among Asian Institute of Medical Science and Technology students (AIMST). The overall perception of mobile phone hazard in AIMST university students was 62%. Most subjects agreed that mobile phone usage can cause headache, loss of mental attention and sleeping disturbances and most

disagree that mobile phone usage can cause constipation and diarrhea. Out of the 124 subjects who were aware of the side effects, 5% of the males and 10% of the females felt that there was no need to minimize the unwanted effects. Siegrist, Earle, Gutscher and Keller (2006) studied the perceptions of risks associated with mobile phones, base stations and other sources of Electromagnetic Fields (EMF). Results showed people who use their mobile phones frequently perceived lower risks and higher benefits than people who use their mobile phones infrequently.

Ezemenaka (2013) studied usage and perceived effect of internet enabled phones on the academic performance of the tertiary students using University of Ibadan students in Nigeria as a case study. The study was carried out in order to understand and bring to fore if the students' academic performance is affected due to the screen time especially during class hours which has a general perception as a medium of distractions to students. It was discovered that students do not perceive internet enabled phone usage to have any negative effect on their academic performance. Syed, Hashim, Maisarah, Che Aniza, Sallehuddin and Nor Asiah (2013) carried out a study to explore and identify the impact of internet addictions on young adults in Malaysia. Findings show that the adults using internet excessively perceive some problems such as interpersonal problem, behavioral problem, physical problem, psychological problem, and work problem in their daily life. However, the young adults believed that the internet usage could help them to improve their skills for doing their work better rather than have any negative effect.

The forgone review revealed that in the existing body of literature on screen time, not many and specific studies have been conducted in relation to screen time and its risks among Nigerian undergraduates. Most of the studies on risks associated with digital devices and internet use were conducted in developed nations like United States, the United Kingdom and Australia. The few studies conducted in Nigeria focused on internet use pattern on undergraduates in the country but without cognizance to inherent risks associated with such screen base devices. The few indigenous studies like Adum *et al* (2016) that studied screen time and its implication among students in Nigeria limits itself to health implication of screen time on Southeast region. Therefore, it is important to further investigate other dimensions of the risks of screen time as well as other students in different parts of Nigeria considering the fact that almost all students across the nation share similar characteristics in relation to exposure to screen devices, as such all are affected to risks associated to screen time.

Theoretical Framework

The significance of theories in every research exercise cannot be overemphasized. Theories enable researchers to explain phenomenon happening in the society. Emergence of new media gadgets viz-a-

viz screen-based devices and internet has attracted several theories that are used to explain different phenomenon associated with them. In the same vein, this study is anchored on Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) and Problematic Computer Use (PCU) theory. TAM is used in the work to explain why students adopt screen-based devices while PCU is used to explain the inherent risks in these devices.

Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)

Davis propounded this model in 1986 to explain why a user accepts or rejects information technology (Park, 2009). According to Davies, perceived usefulness and ease of use of technology are the construct elements of TAM and factors that determine acceptance or rejection of any technology (Wu, Tao and Yang, 2008 cited in Chuttur 2009). Perceived usefulness (PU) is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular device would enhance his or her job performance while Perceived ease-of-use (PEOU) is the degree to which a person believes that using a particular device would be free from effort (Davis 1989). TAM also proposes that external factors affect intention and actual use of technology. Thus, it provides a basis with which one traces how external variables influence belief, attitude, and intention to use. The model has been widely applied to various types of technologies and (Venkatesh et al. 2003).

TAM has been widely criticized. Criticisms of TAM as a "theory" include its questionable heuristic value, limited explanatory and predictive power, triviality, and lack of any practical value (Chuttur 2009). Despite the criticism above, the model (TAM) remains relevant in explaining technology use especially among students. This is because the theory encompasses elements from theories like uses and gratification theory (Katz, Blumler and Gurevitch, 1974), Compensatory theory (David, 2014) and ACE (Accessibility, Control and Excitement) model (Wu, Tao and Yang, 2008) which can be used to explain rationale behind adoption of a medium or devices. Thus, the model fits the current study in that it will explain rationale regarding growing exposure to screen devices among students in Northeast Nigeria. It is assumed that the usefulness and easiness of screen devices also contribute to adoption of screen-based devices and by extension increases screen time among the students which could expose them to many risks.

Problematic Computer Use (PCU) Model

Kimberly Young first proposed the idea of problematic computer use in her seminal paper in 1996 as an extension of internet addiction hypothesis. Research on problematic use of Information technologies remains fragmented; some researchers like Caplan (2010) proposed research models and empirically examined the relationships among the key constructs. PCU model explains the use of computer devices that may be health endangering and may cause immediate or later negative physical

or psychological health outcomes or disturb well-being of users. Simply put, PCU model is concerned with effects of dependence on computers on the user.

Kim and Davis (2009) argue that PCU lacks internal consistency that is basic feature of a theory. Despite this criticism, PCU remains relevant in helping researchers explain the inherent risks associated with obsession with technology devices. In relation to this study, PCU model captures the argument that constant use of screen-based devices lives the students (users) with certain implications, which cut across health, social, physical and psychological wellbeing. Therefore, it is the understanding and right perception about inherent problems of screen time that would help the user take proactive measures or develop healthy use of the screen based devices.

Research Methodology

This study adopts survey design, with undergraduate university students in northeast geopolitical zone of Nigeria as the study population. Northeast geopolitical zone is comprised of Adamawa, Bauchi, Borno, Gombe, Taraba and Yobe States. According to Universities' statistical Digest 2017, there are thirteen universities in the region. The report further states that the total number of undergraduates in the region is one hundred and ninety thousand (190,000) which represent 10% of the total number of undergraduates (1.9 million) in Nigeria (Wahab, 2018). For the purpose of this study, Modibbo Adama University of Technology (MAUTECH), Yola and Taraba State University, Jalingo (TSUJ) were randomly selected via balloting.

A sample size of 450 respondents was selected based on the ranking of sample sizes by Comrey and Lee (1992) as follows: 100=poor, 200=fair, 300=good, 400=very good and 500 and above=excellent (Wimmer and Dominick, 2009). Thus, the sample size (450) is considered sufficient enough to gather data and draw generalization. The sample was divided proportional between the two selected universities. MAUTECH has seven schools with a population of undergraduate reaching 15,801 (n=286) and TSUJ has seven faculties with a population of 9,030 students (n=164). Accidental sampling method was used in selecting respondents for the study. Data gathered from the respondents was analyzed using descriptive statistical tools.

Data Presentation and Analysis

This part of the work presents the data resulting from the study. Originally, 450 copies of the questionnaire were administered but 437 were returned valid (97.1% returned rate) and used in the analysis below. Tables, bar charts and pie charts were used to present the data.

Distribution of the Respondents' Educational Level in Percentages

The above figure indicates that there was representation of respondents from each of the various levels or class of the respondents. The data show that 100 level has 20.4% representation, 200 level has 20.6%, 300 level has 22.9%, 400 level has 18.8% and 500 level has 17.3%. This therefore means that the findings are fair enough for generalization.

Distribution of the Respondents' Gender in Percentages

Out of the total sample of 437 respondents, 285 (65.2%) were male and 152 (34.8%) were female. This finding is indicative of the poor enrolment of female ones into formal school in the northern region of Nigeria.

Age of Respondents

Figure 4.3 above shows that majority of the respondents were youths within the age bracket of 21-25. This is not surprising because majority of university undergraduates nowadays are between the age brackets of 17 - 30. Similarly, this coincided with the findings of the study of the International World Statistics (2011) which observed that youths constitute the majority of the internet users as early adopters, while the older generation is laggards.

Table 1: Distribution of Students' Ownership and Accessibility of Screen-Devices

	Ownership of Mobile phone, Smart-phone or tablet	Ownership of PC or Laptop	Ownership of PSP Game gadget	Access to Commercial cyber cafes
Yes	100%	47.8%	17.4%	21.7%
No	0	52.2%	82.6%	78.3%
Total	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)

The respondents were asked battery of questions on ownership of mobile phone/Smart-phone or tablet, ownership of PC or Laptop, ownership of PSP Game gadget, and access to commercial cyber cafes. As can be seen in Table 1 above, every respondent (100%) own at least mobile phone, smart-phone or tablet, 47.8% owns PC or laptop, 17.4% has PSP game gadget while 21.7% patronized commercial cyber cafes. The data presented above answers the first research question, which sought to know the extent undergraduate students in Northeast Nigeria are exposed to electronic screen-based devices. These findings indicate that the students are exposed to screen-based devices, as majority of them own the devices, which may entail regular use. It also supports the finding of Omenugha (2010) that mobile phones and internet are the most prevalent new media used by the students within the university environment.

Table 2: Frequency of Screen Devices use among Respondents

Options	How often do you use your screen device?	How often do you visit commercial cyber cafes?
Frequently	62.2%	4.3%
Occasionally	26.1%	74%
Rarely	11.7%	21.7%
Total	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)

Having established the purposes why the students use screen-based devices, Data in table 2 above show that more than half of the respondents (62.2%) make frequent use of screen devices; 26.1% utilize the devices occasionally while 11.2% rarely make use of the devices. Additionally, only 4.3% frequently patronize commercial cyber cafes, 74% occasionally patronize commercial cafes while 21.7 rarely patronize commercial cafes. This is an indication that respondents' personal devices are

their major source of screen time. The finding also coincides with the findings in Table 2, where majority of the respondents affirmed ownership of screen devices. Thus, there is tendency of high exposure to the devices due to their closeness to the students.

Table 3: Respondents’ awareness and perception of risks associated with screen based-devices

	I know that too much use of Screen devices has health risks	I know that too much attention to Screen devices can lead to physical accident	I know that too much use of screen devices is harmful to me	I consider risks of screen devices	I Need to regulate my use of screen devices	I made effort to regulate use of screen devices
Yes	100%	100%	100%	47.8%	100%	39.1%
No	0	0	0	52.2%	0%	60.9%
Total	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)	100% (n = 437)

Given the need to determine the respondents’ awareness of risks associated with the use of screen devices, data in table 3 above have shown that all the students are aware of the health implications associated with use of the Screen devices. In the same vein, all of the respondents are aware of physical risk associated with screen time and all of them acknowledge that screen devices and or screen time is harmful. This findings answered research question two which is on respondents’ awareness of risks associated with the use screen devices. Furthermore, to answer research three which is on perception of respondents toward the risks associated with use of screen devices, the table 3 further shows that less than half (47.8%) of the respondents ever considered these risks but all (100%) of them acknowledged the need for control of their use of screen-based devices. Sadly, only 39.1% ever made any effort to mitigate excessive use of their screen-based devices. This is an indication that despite knowledge of the risks associated with use of screen-based devices among students, percentage and attitude toward these risks are not favorable as many do not take any precautionary measures against these risks.

Discussion of Findings

The data revealed that undergraduates in Northeast Universities Nigeria are well exposed to screen-based devices. All of them (100%) have at least a mobile phone. This concurs with findings of Thornton and Houser, (2005) that most students on university campuses carry mobile phones, either for reading e-mails, texting messages, accessing the web or making phone calls. Other findings

similarly to the current findings include (Adum *et al*, 2016 and BSU, 2009). However, less than half of the students own Laptop or PC. Reasons may not be far from the findings of Sinisalo and Karjaluoto (2009) that students prefer the latest smart-phones than laptops and PCs due to their (smart-phones) portability and available services, which include Multimedia Messages, word processing, and internet enablement among others. Ownership of PSP Game gadget and access to commercial cyber cafes are very low among the students. This finding indicates that undergraduates in Northeast Universities of Nigeria are well exposed to screen devices at personal level, thus, the level of screen time is likely to be high due to the students' closeness to their personal devices at all time.

On the awareness of the respondents regarding risks of screen time, data revealed that the students (100%) were aware of the health, physical and social implications associated with use of screen based devices. This is in line with the findings of Adum *et al* (2016) that students in Southeast Nigeria knew the health implication of digital screen technologies and nearly all of them (99%) experienced the health challenge, which attests to a high-level effect of the technologies on the users. The findings also corroborate Uysal (2015) study on Problematic Facebook among Turkish university students where the respondents acknowledged that they knew the problems associated with excessive "facebooking" which is also part screen time.

It was further revealed that despite high awareness of the risks associated with screen time, the perception of the students towards these risks is not favorable. Data show that only less than half (47.8%) of the respondents ever reconsidered the issue usage of screen devices to mitigate dangers associated with screen time. More so, only 39.1% of the respondents have ever done anything to regulate their use of screen devices. This result supports the findings of Kumar, Chuan, Rajendaran (2011) that AIMST university students felt that there was no need to minimize their use of screen devices despite the perceived risks. In addition, it also concurs with the study by Ezemenaka (2013) which discovered that students in University of Ibadan do not believe that screen time (or internet enabled phone usage) have any negative effect on their academic performance.

Conclusion

The research examined awareness and perception of risks associated with screen time among undergraduates in Northeast Universities in Nigeria. It is evident from the study that screen devices like mobile phones and laptops are very useful to undergraduate students in both their personal and academic life. The usage of screen-based devices and internet by students cannot be outlawed but there is need to continuously inform the students on the positive and negative effects of the use of

screen devices. This is important if not, screen devices with their numerous benefits will do a lot of damage to students.

Recommendations

Against the backdrop of the findings, and conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made.

1. There is need for robust sensitization and or education of students toward responsible use of screen-based devices. This should start from the home where by parents guide the children's exposure to screen devices as well as educate them of the importance of regulating their screen time against inherent risks.
2. Management of the various Universities in Northeast Nigeria should regularly organized lectures, teachings, seminars and conferences to enlighten their students about risks of screen time and precautionary measures.
3. Risks of Screen time and precautionary measures like reducing the brightness of the device; keeping device at a safe distance, among others should be written boldly and placed in hostels, classrooms and other places to remind the students to be proactive in safeguarding themselves from the risks of screen-based devices.
4. Government agencies and groups protecting consumer safety like Consumer Council of Nigeria, Standard Organization of Nigeria (SON) should compel producers of mobile screen-devices to improve safety measures like in-built screen light guard in their product right from manufacturing stage and to join the campaign on the need for regulated screen time among young people.

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